

EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERNAL CONTROLS IN ENHANCING ACCOUNTABILITY IN COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES IN BENUE STATE

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Abstract: This study empirically examined the effectiveness of internal controls in enhancing accountability in cooperatives within the Akperan Orshi Polytechnic community in Benue State. Cooperatives are an important source of affordable finance for low- and medium-income earners worldwide, but their long-term survival depends on proper management. Effective and efficient internal control systems play a crucial role in supporting cooperative operations. Guided by specific research objectives, questions, and hypotheses, the study adopted a quantitative, non-experimental correlational design. A total of 108 cooperative employees were selected through total population sampling, and a well-structured questionnaire was used to measure internal control and accountability. Data were analyzed using Mean, Pearson *r*, and Regression Analysis. Findings revealed a very high level of internal control across all indicators and a similarly high level of accountability among cooperatives. Results further showed that internal control is significantly correlated with accountability, with a *p*-value below the level of significance. Overall, internal control had a significant influence on accountability, with control activities emerging as the strongest predictor. The study recommends that management should ensure proper tracking of variances, apply back flush techniques where necessary, and adhere strictly to established accountability procedures within the cooperative sector.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

In business and economic theory, the industrial revolution has some catalytic

impacts. This led to the shift of focus from widening territorial boundaries to economic development in most organizations (Tapang & Oti, 2019). In addition to providing support

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and simply providing a conducive environment for business activities, management is also active in fraud prevention and control along with others. This agency strongly promotes efficient coordination and monitoring, making it necessary to recognize the level of results in performing delegated duties, testing organizational record manipulation and consistency.

Effective internal control is important to all business organizations and more so the cooperative sector whose business environment is prone to risks that must be mitigated for performance and profitability. External stresses in the corporate and social lives of people around the globe are immense. There are in reality disappointments in various relationships whether it is marriage, friendship or company. Man is insatiable and invents various strategies to defraud the organizations in which they operate in industry or in which they trade. Organizations are suffering market problems that are often manmade, and should be prevented.

Cooperative financing has been a major source of finance to many people in Nigeria especially salaried workers. Almost every tertiary institution in Nigeria has cooperative societies to cater for the financing need of their members. Different categories of staff were employed by these tertiary institutions which include academic staff, non-academic staff, technical staff and senior staff. These staff usually arranged themselves into different cooperative societies in order to save money for

future capital budget such as paying their children school fees, buying cars, building houses, purchase of landed properties and so on. (Asiligwa & Rennox, 2017).

Effective internal control system in any cooperative society should evolve over time and should have positive effect on the cooperative society performance. However, not all cooperative societies in have efficient internal control measures in place and as such some are still struggling with liquidity problems, untimely financial reports, inefficient accountability for the cooperative's financial resources, frauds and misuse of the cooperative's resources as well as a number of decisions made not yielding the expected results (Ejoh & Ejom, 2014).

Internal control systems within cooperatives are designed to ensure accountability, transparency, and good governance practices. They encompass mechanisms for risk assessment, internal audit, and compliance with legal and regulatory requirements (Cook and Iliopoulos, 2017). Similarly, the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO, 2018) defines internal control system as a process, effected by an entity's board of directors, management, and other personnel, designed to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of objectives in the following categories: effectiveness and efficiency of operations, reliability of financial reporting, and compliance with applicable laws and regulations. By implementing robust internal

control systems, agricultural cooperatives can improve operational performance of these cooperatives.

Environmental control refers to the management of factors within an organization's surroundings that can affect its operations, processes, and outcomes. This includes measures to monitor, mitigate, and adapt to environmental conditions such as air quality, water resources, waste management, and biodiversity conservation (Environmental Protection Agency Nigeria, 2020). Effective environmental control measures, such as sustainable land management, water conservation techniques, and integrated pest management, contribute to increased crop yields, improved product quality, and reduced environmental impact (Farming Systems Support Services Limited, 2021).

For risk assessment control, Akande and Adegbite (2018) stated that risk assessment control involves identifying, analyzing, evaluating, and mitigating risks that could impact the cooperative's operations, finances, reputation, and strategic objectives. Uzohuo (2022) added that one key aspect of the relationship between risk assessment control and accountability is improved risk management. By conducting comprehensive risk assessments, cooperatives can identify and prioritize risks based on their likelihood and potential impact. This enables them to develop risk mitigation strategies, contingency plans, and resilience measures tailored to specific risks, thereby reducing

vulnerabilities and enhancing operational stability. Financial controls are crucial for ensuring the accuracy, reliability, and integrity of financial information and transactions within cooperative businesses. These controls may include budgetary controls, accounting controls and cash controls among others (Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria, 2019). Also, in financial control, implementing budgets for various activities within the cooperative helps in controlling costs and optimizing resource allocation. This helps in monitoring and approving expenses to ensure they are in line with the budget and are legitimate business expenses to improve accountability.

Effective communication control is instrumental in shaping the accountability of cooperatives in Benue and Nigeria at large, impacting various aspects such as productivity, collaboration, decision-making, and overall efficiency. Bijman (2020) posited that communication control enables cooperatives to make informed decisions based on timely and reliable information. Clear channels of communication ensure that critical information regarding market trends, input availability, pricing, and regulatory requirements is communicated promptly to decision-makers within the cooperative. This facilitates agile decision-making, risk management, and strategic planning, ultimately enhancing accountability and competitiveness.

In view of the above, it has become evident that accountability is indeed paramount to

cooperatives in Nigeria which Benue State is not an exception as it directly impacts their efficiency, effectiveness, and overall success. However, when there is accountability, this can have far-reaching consequences that affect various aspects of the cooperative's functioning, sustainability, and reputation. This can lead to challenges within a cooperative business. Unfortunately, it appears much attention has not been given to these controls such as financial, operational, compliance and risk management controls in cooperatives in Benue State. It is against this background that this study seeks to examine internal control system and accountability of cooperative business in Benue State Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Cooperative societies are critically important to the growth and development of Nigeria because they provide financing for members to start or support an existing Small and Medium Enterprise (SME), acquire assets like houses, etc. It is because of the important role that cooperatives play in providing finances for its mostly poor members who may not meet the stringent requirements to access loans from the regular financial institutions that various stakeholders like the federal government, through its many agencies including the Bank of Industry (BOI), Nigeria Export-Import Bank (NEXIM) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) have provided financial and non-financial support in form of loans, capacity development, etc. to cooperatives. The numerous assistance and support provided for these cooperatives

will not achieve the purpose for which they were provided if the cooperatives do not have effective and efficient internal control system, amongst others, to aid their performance. It is common knowledge that many cooperatives are poorly managed hence leading to poor performance and inability to effectively achieve the objective for which they were set up.

However, poor accountability can strain internal relationships and teamwork within the cooperative. Inefficient processes, unclear roles and responsibilities, or lack of communication channels can lead to conflicts among employees, reduced morale, and decreased productivity. This can hinder collaboration, innovation, and overall organizational cohesion, impacting the cooperative's ability to achieve its objectives effectively. Furthermore, as far as the researcher is aware, no empirical study has investigated the effectiveness of internal control in enhancing accountability of cooperative societies in Benue State. It is against this backdrop that this study intends to bridge the gap by investigating the effectiveness of internal controls in enhancing accountability in cooperatives in Benue State, Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the effectiveness of internal controls system in enhancing accountability in cooperatives in Benue State. Specifically, this study seeks to:

1. Assess the level of internal control of cooperatives in the study area.
2. Assess the level of accountability of cooperatives in the study area.

3. determine the significance of the relationship between the internal controls and accountability of cooperatives

4. Identify which domain of internal control best influences the accountability of cooperatives.

5. make recommendations base on the findings of the study

1.4 Research Questions

This study seeks to proffer responses to the follow research questions.

1. What is the connection between control environment component of internal control and accountability in cooperatives?
2. Does control activities component of internal control system have any effect on the accountability in cooperatives?
3. What effect does monitoring has on the accountability in cooperative?

1.5 Hypotheses of the Study

The study will test the following null hypotheses at 0.05 significant level.

1. Ho₁: There is no significant relationship exists between control environment and accountability in cooperatives.
2. Ho₂: The no significant relationship between control activities component of internal control system and accountability in cooperatives.
3. Ho₃: Monitoring component of internal control and accountability in cooperatives are not significantly related.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Internal Control System

Internal controls refer to processes and

procedures instituted by an organization to ensure the integrity of financial and accounting information, promote accountability, and mitigate risks. They encompass a range of activities, including authorization, verification, and monitoring of transactions.

According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO, 2019), internal control systems are the whole system of controls, financial or otherwise, established by the management in order to carry on the business of the enterprise in an orderly and efficient manner, ensure adherence to management policies, safeguard the assets, and secure as far as possible the completeness and accuracy of the records.

2.1.2 Accountability in Cooperatives

Accountability in cooperatives refers to the obligation of the cooperative's management and members to provide accurate information about the organization's activities, decisions, and financial performance. It involves:

- 1. Transparency:** Open communication regarding operations, finances, and decision-making processes.
- 2. Responsibility:** Management and members are responsible for their actions, ensuring they align with the cooperative's goals and values.
- 3. Answerability:** Stakeholders must be able to explain and justify decisions and actions to members and regulatory bodies.
- 4. Participation:** Encouraging member involvement in governance and decision-

making processes to ensure that their interests are represented.

In the study of Selaratana (2009) about accountability in Thailand's public sector, it was mentioned that in other countries and in different languages, the word accountability is used interchangeably with words such as responsibility and transparency. Nonetheless, it was quoted that accountability is an obligation, or responsibility of a person or organizations or entities to explain, answer, justify, and defend their actions or what they have done to another party who will observe, evaluate, and scrutinize that performance and they can give feedback,

including reward and punishment. Effective accountability fosters trust, enhances member engagement, and promotes the overall success of the cooperative. Accountability in cooperatives is vital for maintaining member trust and ensuring efficient operations. It encourages responsible management of resources and fosters a culture of transparency, which is essential for attracting new members and sustaining existing ones. As illustrated in Figure 1.1, balancing internal controls with accountability requires aligning monitoring activities with clear reporting structures.

Balancing Internal Controls and Accountability

Figure 1.1: Balancing Internal Controls and Accountability

2.1.3 Cooperatives

Generally, a cooperative may be defined as an association of persons who pool their resources together on mutual basis to solve specific

socio-economic problems, which may include income generating activities (Abia, 2000). A cooperative can also be seen as a self- help organization (Adebawojo, Enyi & Adebawo,

2015). These associations may be formed by either producers or consumers. The initiative to form such cooperatives usually arises from one or two people. These initiators then play an advocacy role and enlist other people to the co-operative.

2.1.4 Control environment

It is defined as set of processes, standards, and structures that provides the foundation for the implementation and continuity of the whole system of internal control. Further, an appropriate control environment will create a positive atmosphere that will set the rhythm of an organization so that everyone becomes aware of the relevance of the internal control. Likewise, since internal control is set up by the management, if they believe that having internal control is extremely important, then all personnel will feel the same way. In short, control environment helps an organization to set the tone in implementing effective internal control (Yurniwati & Rizaldi, 2015).

2.1.5 Control activities

As mentioned by Gaku (2014), these are policies and procedures that ensure the organization carries out the management directives. It is measured by presence or absence of approvals, authorizations, verifications, reconciliations, reviews of operating performance, security of assets and segregation of duties. If control activities are not well-sighted by the management, it will cause the internal control to fail.

2.1.6 Risk assessment

It is a process of identification, analysis and evaluation. Besides, risk identification is the first step of risk assessment, followed by risk analysis and lastly, risk evaluation. Risk identification involves finding, recognizing and recording risks which covers identification of asset values which contains maintenance, development and security of assets, threats which are external influence and can occur by accident or on purpose, while vulnerabilities is an internal influence resulting from an ineffective and neglected security. Both can give incidents of breach of security, and existing controls which provides listings and statuses of implemented and planned security controls (Chen, 2015; Eskelinen, 2016).

2.1.7 Information and communication

As noted by Abiola (2013), information and communication ensure that the relevant information, outside and inside of the organization, are communicated well. With that, all information must be identified, captured and communicated in a form, and responsible personnel are given enough time for them to carry out their duties and responsibilities.

2.1.8 Monitoring

Indicator of internal control which refers to the set of procedures and standards in assessing the quality of control which covers ongoing and periodical evaluations of the external supervision of internal controls by the management or other parties who are outside the process (Abiola, 2013). The monitoring part will tell the organization if their internal control

is properly implemented or if it is still effective and whether there are corrective actions that should be taken within the organization.

2.1.9 Participation

It is defined by Dossing, Letshego, and Weideman (2011) as the processes in the systems that obviously accord space and time to involve the public through meetings, assemblies, consultations even through delegating certain decisions or activities for the awareness of the public. An organization to be accountable should enable stakeholders to play an active role in the decision-making processes and activities which may affect them (Blagescu, de las Casas & Lloyd, 2005).

2.1.10 Evaluation

Blagescu *et al.* (2005) defined it as the processes through which an organization, with the involvement of key stakeholders, monitors

and reviews its progress and results against goals and objectives; feeds learning from this back into the organization on an ongoing basis; and reports on the results of the process. Evaluation ensures that the organization has learned from and is also accountable for its performance. In short, the relationship between accountability and evaluation centers on learning. The evaluation process and the results which come after it will help the organization on future decision-making by providing information to improve its performance, thus making it more accountable to achieve its goals and objectives. As shown in Table 1.1, key constructs of cooperatives and internal control components can be represented through keywords and phrases that highlight their operational and accountability dimensions.

Table 1.1: Keywords Matrix of Cooperatives and Internal Control Components

Domain	Construct	Keywords / Phrases	Analytical Relevance
Cooperative Systems	Cooperatives	Voluntary association, pooled resources, mutual support, income-generation, producer/consumer, initiators, advocacy, member-driven	Context, organizational foundation, socio-economic empowerment
COSO 1	Control Environment	Ethical tone, management commitment, governance integrity, organizational values, leadership philosophy, staff awareness	Foundation for internal control, shapes compliance culture
COSO 2	Control Activities	Policies, procedures, approvals,	Operationalizes

		authorizations, verifications, reconciliations, asset security, segregation of duties, performance review	directives, ensures accountability, risk mitigation
COSO 3	Risk Assessment	Risk identification, risk analysis, risk evaluation, asset values, threats, vulnerabilities, control measures, prioritization	Detects threats, informs mitigation strategies, operational stability
COSO 4	Information & Communication	Data capture, reporting, internal/external flow, timeliness, relevance, accessibility, feedback channels	Transparency, informed decision-making, accountability support
COSO 5	Monitoring	Ongoing evaluation, periodic assessment, supervisory review, external oversight, corrective actions, control quality	Continuous improvement, control effectiveness, compliance verification
Accountability	Participation	Stakeholder engagement, meetings, consultations, assemblies, delegated decisions, involvement, inclusivity	Enhances democratic governance, transparency, legitimacy
Accountability	Evaluation	Goal assessment, performance review, learning loops, stakeholder feedback, decision-making improvement, reporting	Performance accountability, learning, informed future planning

2.2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.2.1 The System Theory

This study is anchored on the system theory as propounded by Von Bertalanffy in 1968. The early proponent of the system theory was Ludwig Von Bertalanffy, a biologist, and Kenneth Boulding, an economist. He developed the systems theory in response to the

increasing fragmentation and duplication of scientific and technological research and decision making in the first half of the 20th century. The System Theory is a collection of ideas and principles of several theories of diverse disciplinary backgrounds; it has as its subject matter the formulation and derivation of those principles which are valid for

“systems” in general.

System theory is a general science of “wholeness” which up till now was considered a vague, hazy, and semi metaphysical concept. The major aims (assumptions) of general systems theory are; there is a general tendency towards integration in the various sciences, natural and social, such integration seems to be centred in a theory of systems, such theory may be an important means for aiming at exact theory in the non-physical fields of science. Developing unifying principles running “vertically” through the universe of the individual sciences, this theory brings us nearer to the goal of the unity of science, this can lead to a much-needed integration in scientific education.

The systems theory is now generally used and applied in all aspects of life and virtually all disciplines. The general system theory views systems, whether biological, solar, physical or organizational, as a ‘whole’ even though they are made of various components. Thus, a system is a set of elements or components that are interrelated to one another in such a manner that they form a discernable whole and tend to achieve common objectives. We are interested in the general systems theory to obtain a better understanding of internal control which is a sub-system within a larger system the organization.

2.3 Empirical Studies

A number of studies have been carried out on

internal control and performance of organizations but just few have centred on cooperative societies. Some of the studies reviewed are examined below with a view to relating them to the current study, establishing a common ground and identifying differences. Eniola (2020) analyzed internal control procedures and the performance of the organization in Nigeria’s south-west region. The study framework was developed on the basis of an in-depth review of the literature and in accordance with stakeholder theory. The analysis followed a qualitative approach to descriptive research design. Multiple regression models were used to check whether there is any impact on financial performance. The findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between internal audit control, risk management and monitoring practices. Odek and Okoth (2019) analyzed the effects of internal control systems on financial performance of small and medium distribution companies. The study was anchored on Agency and Reliability theory, and a conceptual framework showing the interaction between internal control systems and financial performance. Correlational and case study design was adopted while employing census survey technique. Primary data was collected using questionnaires and secondary data was collected from relevant books, journals and periodicals. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation and inferential statistics such as Pearson’s correlation and multiple regression analysis was employed to analyze

the data. Presentation was done by the use of tables and charts. The results of the study may help identify gaps within the systems of internal control at Moon bluez Enterprises Limited and in the distribution industry at large especially among small and medium sized entities.

Tapang and Oti (2019) examined internal audit and financial performance of micro finance banks in Nigeria. The study made use of secondary sources which were analyzed using the ordinary least square technique. The results revealed that the regression parameters estimated coefficient has a positive sign and is therefore consistent with our a-priori expectation.

Umar and Dikko (2018) examined the effect of

internal control systems on the performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. A survey method was employed and the study used stratified random sampling. The findings of the study revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between the four components of internal control (control environment, control activities, monitoring and risk assessment) and performance. **Table 2.1** presents a summary of key empirical studies on internal control and organizational performance. The table highlights the theoretical anchors, methodologies, sample populations, data analysis techniques, major findings, limitations, and relevance of each study to the current research.

Table 2.1: Summary of Empirical Studies on Internal Control and Organizational Performance

Theoretical Anchor	Methodology	Sample / Population	Data Analysis	Key Findings	Limitations	Relevance to Current Study
Stakeholder Theory	Qualitative	Org. in South-West	Regression	Positive link: audit, risk, monitoring	Regional; descriptive only	Shows internal control role; partly applies to cooperatives
Agency & Reliability	Correlational	SMEs distribution	Mean, SD, correlation, regression	Internal control affects performance; gaps	Limited to SMEs	Shows control in SMEs; indirectly informs

			on	found		cooperative s
Not stated	Ex-post facto	Microfinanc e banks	OLS regressi on	Positive link; matches expectations	Only secondary data	Confirms audit helps performanc e; useful for monitoring
Not stated	Survey	Commercial banks	Correlat ion & regressi on	Control components positively affect performanc e	Banks may differ from cooperatives	Shows control component effect; partly applies to cooperative s

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study make do of quantitative, non-experimental research design with the application of correlational technique which involves collecting a standard range of quantitative data from a significant sample of respondents through use of survey questionnaires.

3.2 Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Benue State with a focus on the Polytechnic community Akperan Orshi Polytechnic Yandev and Benue State is one of the 36 states located in North Central Nigeria.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised of the entire staff or employee totally 108 from four cooperative societies within the Polytechnic

community were used in the study.

3.4 Sampling and Sampling Technique

This study employed the total population sampling which included all employees from four cooperatives societies sample purposively in the polytechnic community in Yandev. Simply, the researcher decides what needs to be known and sets out to find people who can and are willing to provide the information by virtue of knowledge or experience.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the respondents through questionnaires instrument were analyzed using the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson r and Regression Analysis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Internal Control of Cooperatives. The level of

internal control of cooperatives as perceived by the employees is shown in Table 3.1. The results revealed that the overall mean was 4.61 with a descriptive level of very high; meaning internal control of cooperatives is always

manifested. The results further revealed that the risk assessment obtained the highest mean of 4.66 while control activities got the lowest mean of 4.57, all with the same descriptive level of very high.

Table 3.1: Level of Internal Control of Cooperatives

Indicator	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Control environment	4.62	0.63	Very High
Control activities	4.57	0.66	Very High
Risk assessment	4.66	0.62	Very High
Information and communication	4.6	0.66	Very High
Monitoring	4.65	0.63	Very High
Overall	4.61	0.65	Very High

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Accountability of Cooperatives Presented in Table 3.2 is the level of accountability of cooperatives in terms of participation, evaluation, and fiscal compliance. The results revealed that the overall mean was 4.60, with a descriptive level of very high. This means that

the accountability of cooperatives is always manifested. The result further revealed that fiscal compliance posted the highest mean of 4.62 and participation obtained the lowest mean of 4.58, all with the same descriptive level of very high.

Table 3.2: Level of Accountability of Cooperatives

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Participation	0.66	4.58	Very High
Evaluation	0.65	4.6	Very High
Fiscal compliance	0.61	4.62	Very High
Overall	0.64	4.6	Very High

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Significance on the Relationship between Internal Control and Accountability of Cooperatives. Presented in Table 3.3 are the results of the test of significance in the relationship between the variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed r-value of 0.804 with a p-value of

0.000, which is significant at 0.05 level. The first null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between internal control and accountability in cooperatives in Yandev, is thus rejected.

Doing a correlation among the indicators of both variables, it can be gleaned that

accountability revealed overall r-values ranging from 0.715 to 0.796 with p-values of 0.000 which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. This showed that the higher the internal control, the higher the accountability in cooperatives in Yandev.

As indicated in the table, control environment, control activities, risk assessment, information and communication, and monitoring were significantly related to overall accountability with computed r-values ranging from 0.697 to 0.793, $p < 0.05$.

Table 3.3: Significance on the Relationship between Internal Control and Accountability

Internal Control	Participation	Evaluation	Fiscal compliance	Overall
Control Environment	0.573** (0.000)	0.708** (0.000)	0.695** (0.000)	0.697** (0.000)
Control activities	0.694** (0.000)	0.773** (0.000)	0.782** (0.000)	0.793** (0.000)
Risk assessment	0.643** (0.000)	0.739** (0.000)	0.704** (0.000)	0.736** (0.000)
Information and communication	0.675** (0.000)	0.721** (0.000)	0.714** (0.000)	0.745** (0.000)
Monitoring	0.717** (0.000)	0.736** (0.000)	0.653** (0.000)	0.744** (0.000)
Overall	0.715** (0.000)	0.796** (0.000)	0.768** (0.000)	0.804** (0.000)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Significance on the Influence of Internal Control on Accountability of Cooperatives Presented in Table 3.4 is the significance on the influence of internal control on accountability of cooperatives in Yandev. It was revealed that the F-value was 41.566 with a p-value of 0.000, which indicate that internal control significantly influences the accountability of cooperatives in Yandev.

The result also displayed an R value 0.819, with an R² value of 0.671, which meant that 67.10

percent of the variance of accountability can be best explained by internal control. The other 32.90 percent can be attributed to the unknow variables. When taken individually, the result showed that the control environment, risk assessment, and information and communication showed no significant influence on accountability in cooperatives. The support of other indicators is needed for the combined influence. Only control activities and monitoring measures of internal control posted

significant influence on accountability. Between the two, control activities emerged as the best predictor of accountability given a higher Beta coefficient of 0.452. This rejects the second

null hypothesis, stating that there is no domain of internal control that best influences the accountability of cooperatives in Yandev.

Table 3.4: Significance of Internal Control and Accountability of Cooperatives

Indicators	B	B	t	Sig.
Control environment	-0.037	-0.037	-0.305	0.761
Control activities	0.452	0.428	2.925	0.004
Risk assessment	0.045	0.043	0.322	0.748
Information and communication	0.128	0.117	0.923	0.358
Monitoring	0.282	0.281	2.942	0.004

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The study revealed that the overall level of internal control is very high, which means that internal control as perceived by the employees of cooperatives is always manifested. The very high result is due to very high rating given by the respondents on control environment, control activities, risk assessment, information and communication, and monitoring. This confirms the pronouncement of Bubilek (2017) along with other authors, Gaku (2014); Vollbehr (2014); and Yurniwatia and Rizaldi (2005) that the presence of control environment, control activities, risk assessment, information and communication, and monitoring will help an organization establish a well-functioning internal control.

For the level of accountability among cooperatives, the results showed that the overall level of accountability is very high. The very high level of accountability of cooperatives in Yandev is due to the very high rating given by the respondents on these cooperative’s fiscal

compliance and evaluation, as well as participation. The management of cooperatives provides adequate information when making accountable reports, conducts resource monitoring and has the right priorities set during the budgeting process. These practices are expected to increase the accountability of cooperatives, as viewed by various authors (Blagescu *et al.*, 2005; Poto & Fornabio, 2017; Marenakos, 2011; Kimaite, 2016) who pronounced that accountability is increased by providing adequate information and having right priorities in implementing internal control, among others.

The results of the study confirmed that internal control has a significant relationship to accountability of cooperatives since the result showed a p-value less the level of significance.

Further, it was added that well-functioning internal control can be manifested by encouraging fraud reporting from employees, and taking suitable actions to counteract for the

future, considering the associated risks and to know how to handle those risks, having internal control of information and communication which addresses the threat of unauthorized access to an information by an insider or outsider, and having periodic assessment or regular reminder to all personnel on how internal control should operate to promote greater accountability.

The result of the study revealed that internal control significantly influences accountability of cooperatives having a p-value of less than the level of significance. The R- squared of sixty-seven-point ten percent means that the variance of accountability can be explained by internal control at around sixty-seven point ten, the other thirty-two-point ninety percent can be attributed to the unknow variables. The result further showed that on the singular level, the control environment, risk assessment and information and communication showed no significant influence on accountability. It requires control activities and monitoring to assimilate influence. On the other hand, control activities and monitoring of cooperatives solely can significantly influence accountability of cooperatives.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following were recommended:

This study examines the role of internal controls in enhancing accountability within

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cooperatives in Nigeria. It discusses the significance of internal control systems, their implementation challenges, and their impact on organizational performance. The findings indicate that effective internal controls not only improve accountability but also foster transparency, trust, and member engagement in cooperative societies.

This study, with the very high level of internal control of cooperatives, suggests that cooperatives use internal control tools on human resources to evaluate the level of productivity, effectiveness and efficiency of its human resources, use the complaints from other stakeholders as a tool of internal control, have plan B for any surprised changes that might affect the work in the cooperative, pass the information and duties by the management to its employees clearly and smoothly and study the received complaint to find out its cause to take the appropriate actions.

That the management should provide tracking variances and back flush and should adhere to accountability procedures governing the cooperative sector.

That the control environment, risk assessment and information and communication be strengthened to satisfy their employees further. It is therefore recommended that further study be conducted to find out what factors significantly influence accountability.

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